

Integrated germplasm improvement – upland

Two improved upland rice varieties for Bangladesh

M. K. Bashar, R. K. Das, M. A. Islam, M. Nasiruddin, and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

BRRI recently released improved upland rice varieties BR20 and BR21 for direct seeded aus season in high-rainfall areas of Bangladesh. BR20 (BR201-193-1) was derived from IR272-4-1-2-J1/IR5; BR21 (BR1656-22-1) came from C22/IET1444. Both varieties have intermediate plant height, short duration, and high yield potential and are moderately resistant to lodging and drought. Both are moderately resistant to bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, rice tungro virus,

brown spot, and grain discoloration.

BR20 averages 133 filled grains/panicle, with 1,000-grain weight of 21 g. BR21 has 112 filled grains/panicle with 1,000-grain weight of 23 g.

The new varieties yielded at least

two times more than existing local upland varieties (Table 1). Physicochemical and cooking qualities of BR20 and BR21 are compared with local popular upland variety Hashikalmi in Table 2. □

Table 1. Average grain yield and some agronomic traits of BR20 and BR21 in direct seeded upland conditions in Bangladesh, 1985-88.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Average grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Increase over local check variety (%)
			On station 1985 (10)	On farm 1986 (23)	Demonstration in farmers' field			Mean	
					1986 (12)	1987 (6)	1988 (70)		
BR20	105-112	110-120	3.8	2.4	3.1	3.2	3.08	3.11	107
BR21	95-105	95-110	3.1	2.5	3.1	3.2	3.06	3.01	101
Local upland variety (check)	90-100	110-115	1.3	1.2	-	1.6	1.85	1.50	-

^aNumbers in parentheses are number of test sites.

Table 2. Physicochemical and cooking qualities of BR20 and BR21.

Variety	Milling outturn (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L/B ratio	Protein (%)	Amylose (%)	Gelatinization temp	Imbibition ratio	Elongation ratio	Size and shape	Endosperm	Tenderness
BR20	73	5.1	2.2	2.3	7.8	26	6.0	4.0	1.5	Medium bold	Translucent	Medium hard
BR21	73	5.2	2.0	2.6	8.3	26	4.5	4.0	1.5	Medium bold	Translucent	Medium hard
Hashikalmi (local check)	72	4.8	2.1	2.3	7.0	29	4.0	3.8	1.4	Short bold	White belly	Hard

Integrated germplasm improvement – deepwater

NDGR402, a promising new floating rice

J. L. Dwivedi, R. V. Singh, and O. P. Verma, Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, India

NDGR402, a pure line selection from local variety Goanth, can withstand gradual increases in water depth up to 2.0-2.5 m. Its grains are short and bold with red kernels, L/B ratio of 2.1, and 1,000-grain weight of 30.9 g. It takes 215 d from seeding to maturity.

It was selected from 13 entries including local selections and promis-

ing lines from cross RP31-49-2/LMN and check variety Jalmagna evaluated for three consecutive seasons 1985-87. Test plots were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were directly sown in Apr in 5- × 2-m plots. Fertilizer was applied 30-30 kg NP/ha as basal and 30 kg N/ha in two equal splits before flooding and at tillering.

NDGR402 (IET10235) gave the highest yield, an average 4.9 t/ha--17% more than check Jalmagna. Plant height ranged from 220 to 311 cm, depending on peak water depth. It showed drought tolerance similar to

Jalmagna (and better than Jaladhi 1) at the vegetative stage and good elongation and kneeing ability at later stages.

Its higher yield potential may be ascribed mainly to number of grains/panicle and more productive tillers (Table 1).

NDGR402 looked promising in All India Rice Improvement Trials at Ghagharaghat, Chinsurah, North Lakhimpur, and Pusa during 1987 wet season and in the Uniform Varietal Trial in 1988. It yielded 4.3 t/ha in 1987 and 2.3 t/ha in 1988 wet season at Ghagharaghat and was superior to checks in 1988 at North Lakhimpur